

The effect of parental income and work expectation on interest in taking master degree in undergraduate students at the economic education department faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

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Abstract

This research renders how parental income and work expectation impacts interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo either partially or simultaneously. The design was quantitative with an ex-post facto method and correlational design. The primary data were collected through questionnaire distribution to students. The data analysis technique was double linear regression using SPSS version 21. The results demonstrated that (1) Parental income positively and significantly influenced interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a coefficient of partial determination of 34.30%, (2) Work expectation positively and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at a coefficient of partial determination of 36.90%, and (3) Parental income and work expectation simultaneously and significantly impacted interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a coefficient of simultaneous determination of 71.20%, and the rest of 28.80% could be illuminated by other variables unanalyzed here, e.g., student competencies in accessing scholarships, commitment to continuing studies, support from lecturers to undergraduate students, and individual income of the graduates. As such, the hypotheses were justified as true and hence acceptable.

Keywords: Interest in Continuing Study; Parental Income; Work Expectation

1. Introduction

As regards interest in taking a further study, according to Rini (2012:2), continuing a study to higher education is excited by interest in and the need for higher knowledge. Individual interest boosts them to carry out an activity and participate in it. Similarly, associated with taking a master degree, graduate interest will encourage them to pursue the degree because of their desire for acquiring higher science and knowledge. In so doing, interest in taking a master degree is affected by various factors.

To begin with, parental income is the first factor. Gerungan (2004:201-202) argues that family condition to the social development of children is not limited to socio-economic status or social integrity and interaction. Ethics and socialization attitudes are likewise vital. Family, that in this case, is parents, play a critical role in shaping their children personality. Parental income is considered crucial as taking a master degree means spending much money. Parental income has two characteristics: allowance for those without income and allowance for those with personal income.

Another factor affecting interest in taking a master degree was work expectation. Solehudin (2016:43) conveys a significant impact of perceived work experience on interest in taking higher education. Individuals have the right for

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determining self-potencies and abilities to use opportunities. Those potencies and abilities are acquired through a range of attempts. In education, individuals have the right for determining to the extent to which their education goes high. Individuals nurturing interest in higher education must be anxious to have a job aligned with their education.

Focusing on interest in taking a master degree in graduates, this research was conducted on undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economy Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Taking a further study is a dream for those graduating from a bachelor's degree. Some prefer working, and others prefer being unemployed to working not commensurate with their expertise with low income.

Table 1 demonstrates the results of our observation of the trend of interest in taking a master's in Economic Education at the Postgraduate Program Universitas Negeri Gorontalo in the last five years.

Table 1 List of New Students Taking A Master's Degree in Economic Education Universitas Negeri Gorontalo

No.	Class = Number of Students	Sex		UNG Alumni	
		L	P	Number	Percentage
1	2017 = 14 students	1	4	8	57.14%
2	2018 = 12 students	4	8	7	58.33%
3	2019 = 10 students	4	6	8	80.00%
4	2020 = 3 students	1	2	1	33.33%
5	2021 = 17 students	6	11	6	35.29%

Data source: siat.pasca.ung.ac.id

Master students at the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo fluctuated by number. The majority of the students were female. Several students had no job. That being so, they hinged on their parents to continue studies. Interest in taking a master's degree in the alumni (graduates) majoring Economic Education was fluctuated. 2019 was the year with the highest number of UNG alumni taking a master's degree at 80.00% of the total students taking a master's degree in Economic Education UNG. And yet, the percentage declined significantly in 2020 and 2021 to 33.33% and 35.29% of the total number of students, respectively. The factor was the COVID-19 pandemic impacting income and work expectation in which people grew their skepticism.

Out of 167 active students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo the class of 2018, 133 relied on father income, 17 relied on mother, and five with low parental income under one million per month. Furthermore, 19 students rested on father income, three anchored on mother income of IDR1-3 million. A student was contingent upon father income of IDR3-5 million, and five depended on mother income. Two students hinged on father income of IDR 5-10 million.

Based on the background, we are interested in examining interest in taking a master degree in students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Gorontalo. We focus on several aspects influential on the interest, i.e., parental income and work expectation. It is commensurate with Taufik & Kurniawati (2020) that socio-economic conditions of parents, especially their income, will positively and significantly augment student interest. Amin et al. (2018) propose a positive and significant correlation between future orientation representing future work expectation and interest in taking a master study. This research offers a distinctive feature, that is the independent variable, analysis complexity, and the higher study intended that is at the same campus, i.e., Universitas Negeri Gorontalo, offering relatively affordable fees but no opportunity to take a master under a scholarship program.

2. Research methodology

The site was at the bachelor's degree program at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. We selected the site because: (1) There was an issue found attributed to the research title, (2) Data collection was more efficient, and (3) Many bachelor graduates took their master's degree in Economic Education. This research was performed for three months, i.e., June-August 2022. The approach was quantitative using an ex-post facto method and correlational design. Primary data were collected through questionnaire distribution. The data analysis technique was double linear regression using SPSS version 21.

3. Research results

3.1. Research Variable Descriptive

The results of the descriptive analyses for research variables are as follows:

- Parental Income Variable (X_1)

Table 2 exhibits respondent perception of the parental income variable.

Table 2 Analysis of Respondent Responses to Parental Income Variable (X_1)

No.	Indicator	Actual	Ideal	Score	Criteria
1	Rentals to wealth	949	1,260	75.32%	Acceptable
2	Salary or wage	920	1,260	73.02%	Acceptable
3	Interest	629	945	66.56%	Acceptable
4	Income from entrepreneurship	877	1,260	69.60%	Acceptable
Total		3,375	4,725	71.43%	Acceptable

Source: Processed Data, 2022

From Table 2, the parental income variable was considered “Acceptable” at a score of 71.43%. It indicated that undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo had parents capable of funding the fees for taking a master degree.

3.2. Work Expectation Variable (X_2)

Respondent perceptions of the work expectation variable are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Analysis of Respondent Responses to Work Expectation Variable (X_2)

No.	Indicator	Actual	Ideal	Score	Criteria
1	Job and work characteristics	749	945	79.26%	Acceptable
2	Competition level	480	630	76.19%	Acceptable
3	Work pressure	493	630	78.25%	Acceptable
4	Compatibility	484	630	76.83%	Acceptable
5	Fairness	503	630	79.84%	Acceptable
6	Work position satisfaction	548	630	86.98%	Good
7	Satisfiers	564	630	89.52%	Good
Total		3,821	4,725	80.87%	Good

Source: Processed Data, 2022

From Table 3, the work expectation variable was considered good at a score of 80.87%.

3.3. Interest in Taking a Master Degree Variable (Y)

Table 4 suggests how respondents perceived the taking a master degree variable.

Table 4 Analysis of Respondent Responses to Interest in Taking a Master Degree Variable (Y)

No.	Indicator	Actual	Ideal	Score	Criteria
1	Personal interest	1,490	1,890	78.84%	Acceptable
2	Situational interest	1,268	1,575	80.51%	Good
3	Psychological interest	1,072	1,260	85.08%	Good
Total		3,830	4,725	81.06%	Good

Source: Processed Data, 2022

In Table 4, the interest in taking a master degree variable was considered “Good” at a score of 81.06%. It suggested that undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo nurtured a high desire for taking a master degree in Economic Education UNG.

3.4. Regression Model Interpretation

Table 5 exhibits the analysis results using SPSS.

Table 5 Regression Analysis Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.675	4.006		-.668	0.507
	Parental income	0.520	0.089	0.471	5.817	0.000
	Work expectation	0.486	0.079	0.498	6.159	0.000

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 21, 2022

According to Table 5, the simple linear regression model built was:

$$\hat{Y} = -2.675 + 0.520X_1 + 0.486X_2 + e$$

The model was interpreted as follows:

$$a = -2.675$$

A constant refers to a fixed value. If parental income and work expectation had no effect, interest in taking a master degree was constant at -2.675 units.

$$b_1 = 0.520$$

The coefficient of regression of variable X_1 (parental income) was 0.520, indicating that 1 unit of changes in the parental income variable would impact interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 0.520 units, under the assumption that the work expectation variable was constant or *ceteris paribus*.

$$b_2 = 0.486$$

The coefficient of regression of variable X_2 (work expectation) was 0.486, pointing out that 1 unit of changes in the work expectation variable would influence interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by 0.486 units, under the assumption that the parental income variable was constant or *ceteris paribus*.

3.5. Partial Hypothesis Test

3.5.1. Effect of Parental Income on Interest in Taking a Master Degree

Table 6 presents the test results for the effect of parental income on interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

Table 6 Partial Test Results for X_1 Effect on Y

Model	(Constant)	Parental Income (Variable X_1)
Coefficient (t-count)	-0.668	5.817
Significance	0.507	0.000
t_{table}		2.000
Description		Significant effect
Significant effect because: $t_{count} > t_{table}$ The significance value < the alpha value 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$)		

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 21, 2022

As shown in Table 6, the t_{count} of the parental income variable was 5.817, and the t_{table} at a 5% significance level and the degree of freedom $n-k-1$ or $63-2-1=60$ was 2.000. If compared, the first > the latter at a t_{table} of $5.817 > 2.000$. As such, at the 95% confidence level, parental income positively and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

3.5.2. Effect of Work Expectation on Interest in Taking a Master Degree

Table 7 suggests the test results for the effect of work expectation on interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

Table 7 Partial Test Results for X_2 Effect on Y

Model	(Constant)	Parental Income (Variable X_2)
Coefficient (t-count)	-0.668	6.159
Significance	0.507	0.000
t_{table}		2.000
Description		Significant effect
Significant effect because: $t_{count} > t_{table}$ The significance value < the alpha value 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$)		

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 21, 2022

Table 7 demonstrates that the t_{count} of the work expectation variable was 6.159, and the t_{table} at a 5% significance level and the degree of freedom $n-k-1$ or $63-2-1=60$ was 2.000. If compared, the first > the latter at a t_{table} of $6.159 > 2.000$. As such, at the 95% confidence level, work expectation positively and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

3.6. Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Table 8 exhibits the simultaneous test results.

As indicated in Table 8, the F_{count} was 74.036. The F_{table} at a 5% significance level and $df_1 = 2$ and $df_2 = N-k-1 = 63$ was 3.150. If compared, the first > the latter at a t_{table} of $5.817 > 2.000$. If compared, F_{count} was higher than F_{table} , and hence, parental income and work expectation simultaneously and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

Table 8 Simultaneous Test Results

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2247.490	2	1123.745	74.036	.000 ^b
	Residual	910.702	60	15.178		
	Total	3158.192	62			

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 21, 2022

3.7. Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is pointed out in Table 9.

Table 9 Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.844 ^a	.712	.702	3.89594

Source: Data Processed Using SPSS 21, 2022

From Table 9, the effect (the ability of the independent variable to lay out the dependent on) using the Adjusted R Square was 0.712. The value indicated that 71.20% of interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo could be set forth by other variables unanalyzed here.

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of Parental Income on Interest in Taking a Master Program

The results pointed out that the parental income variable was “Acceptable” at a score of 71.43%. It showed that undergraduate students in the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo had parents that could afford the fees of taking a master degree. The capability came from parents with sufficient income from rentals to assets and adequate salary or wage. High income of parents enabled them to pay for their children’s fees of taking a master degree in economic education, and income would be proportional to the interest in continuing studies. As such, parental income was a consideration of continuing studies.

High family income would advocate child growth and development. Parents with high income could fulfill their children’s needs, either primary or secondary. Hence, children would develop their intelligence, knowledge, and achievement. It was aligned with Soetjiningsih (2011:16) that parents’ high income would buoy children, particularly during the globalization and modernization eras, when wealth and money were two requisite factors in society. Human needed money to fulfill their needs, either primary or secondary.

The regression test results figured out that parental income positively and significantly impacted interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a coefficient of partial determination of 34.30%. The positive coefficient suggested that parental income promoted interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

It was commensurate with Gerungan (2004:201-202) that family state roles related to social development of children were not limited to the socio-economic status or structure intactness and their interaction. Additionally, ethics and attitudes related to socialization played salient roles. Family, in this care parents, played seminal roles in shaping personalities of their children. Parental income was considered significant to pay the master tuition fees, that was considerably high. Parental income might have two characteristics: financially endorsing their children that had no income and those with personal income after graduating.

4.2. Effect of Work Expectation on Interest in Continuing Studies

The descriptive analysis results of the work expectation variable demonstrated that the variable was considered “Good” at a score of 80.87%. It exhibited that undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo nurtured a high expectation of continuing studies. They were expecting to apply as lecturers or in other better jobs after graduating from master education. These expectations hailed from the fact that there were some state civil apparatus lecturers at Universitas Negeri Gorontalo and private lecturers at Perguruan Tinggi Swasta in Gorontalo Province were master graduates in economic education. It scaled up undergraduate student interest in taking a master degree to achieve the job they were anxious to.

Work expectation referred to interest in a job or profession to attain goals and earn income that could meet needs. Work expectation intended here encompassed the expectations of working in educational planes, e.g., lecturers, civil servant teachers, private teachers, temporary private teachers, instructors and non-educational ones, e.g., private employees, civil servant non-teachers, entrepreneurs, laborers, and others. Nearly all bachelor graduates desired for having jobs after graduating, making them maintain any desire for continuing education.

The regression test results indicated that work expectation positively and significantly affect interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a coefficient of partial determination of 36.90%. The positive coefficient pointed out that higher work expectation nurtured by undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department led to a higher interest in taking a master degree.

It comported with Solehudin (2016) presenting a significant impact of perceived work opportunities on interest in continuing studies to the tertiary level. All individuals maintained two options, i.e., self-potencies and abilities to reach opportunities. Potencies and abilities could be acquired through hard work. Similarly, in education, all individuals could determine to the degree to which they would continue education. Indirectly, individuals with high education were also itching to jobs conforming to the education taken.

4.3. Simultaneous Effect of Parental Income on Work Expectation on Interest in Continuing Studies

The statistical descriptive test results for interest in taking a master degree showed that the variable was considered “Good” at a score of 81.06%. It suggested that undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo retained a high or good desire for taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics UNG. The cause was psychological and situational interests espousing them to continue a further study, future job expectation, and parental income.

From the simultaneous regression test, parental income and work expectation simultaneously and significantly impacted interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo at a coefficient of simultaneous determination to by 71.20%, whereas the rest, 28.80%, could be explained by other variables unexamined here, such as student competencies in accessing scholarships, commitment and determination to continuing studies, lecture support, and personal income of graduates. In so doing, it is of paramount importance to augment student interest taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo by actively giving socialization to students. This task should be carried out by economic education master graduates that have successfully been lecturers or had better careers after graduating from UNG.

It was congruent with Rini (2012:2) that continuing studies to the tertiary level stemmed from interest and needs for developing knowledge. The interest would encourage individuals to conduct a certain action and participation. That being so, bachelor graduate interest in taking a master degree would foester them to seek the way. Therefore, we could say that interest in taking a master degree was influenced by a range of factors.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion, we concluded:

- Parental income positively and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.
- Work expectation positively and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

- Parental income and work expectation simultaneously and significantly affected interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo.

Suggestion

Building on the conclusions, the suggestions we could propose were:

- Students at the Economic Education Faculty of Economics Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo should strive to make achievements and be active in saving, especially those with *Bidikmisi* scholarship or *KIP Kuliah*, helping them continue studies. They should support their parents' businesses or perform business activities (being entrepreneurs) during their bachelor study to pay their tuition fees later.
- Parents of students should endeavor to identify their children's aims to continue studies. It will impel them to save some from their income to finance their children's needs for taking a master degree. Parents with business activities should be productive and must not be consumptive, allowing their children to take a master degree.
- Lecturers the Economic Education Faculty of Economics Department Universitas Negeri Gorontalo should induce students by shedding light on work expectation of master students because students continuing studies after graduating will elevate faculty or university IKU achievement scores.
- Student interest in taking a master degree in undergraduate students at the Economic Education Department Faculty of Economics Universitas Negeri Gorontalo should be actively enhanced by giving them socialization. It is the task and responsibilities that should be fulfilled by economic education master graduates that have successfully been lecturers or had better careers after graduating from UNG.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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